

STUDY OF EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTES REGARDING PROVISIONS AND FACILITIES FOR LEARNING DISABLE STUDENTS

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1. Introduction:

Education aims to develop students in all areas like intellectual, physical, mental, emotional, social, moral etc. It is effective system of development of student's abilities, skills, attitudes and values. In spite of this effective system and process somehow all the aims cannot be fulfilled by all the students. Some students are exceptional in it. We know that every student is unique and learners are diverse in nature, their needs and expectations are different from education. They do not expect same education for all, So Education should be given as per the needs of the learner. Special education provides need based education to the students who has different abilities. Special education as 'specifically designed instruction that meets the unusual needs of special children'. Learning disabilities is one of major challenging part of special education. (A.G.Reddy,R.Ramas,A. Kusum, 2006). We found learning disabilities not only in India but in the world. It is worldwide area of special education. The "Warnock committee report in 1978 broadened the concept of special education. It evolved the various forms of physical and intellectual impairment result in special educational needs. It was at parents meeting in New York City in the early 1960s that this term was proposed by Samuel kirk as a compromise because of the confusing variety of labels that were being used for normal intelligence who was having learning disabilities. In those days such a child was likely to be referred to as being minimally brain injured, slow learner, a dyslexic. (Hallahan and Kauffman 1991).Hence this label learning disabilities was accepted by parents whose children were having this type of problems.

There are many individuals who purportedly had severe learning disabilities but still they have done a great work for society. Thomas Edison, George patton. Woodrow Wilson, Albert Einstein (Thompson,1971) even one of the world's most famous writer of children's literature Hans Christian Anderson had a severe reading disability but he proved that one can be successful inspite of having disability (Arden,1979)

There are many organizations in the world which are working on learning disabilities. Such as Association for children with learning disabilities (ACLD), New York, International Academy for Research in learning disabilities (IARLD),1976 U.S.A, Welsh center for learning disabilities (WCLD),wales.

In the National level there are some policies which have made provisions for learning disabilities. The National Policy of Education in India (1986) recommended a) Education for children with locomotors and other mild disabilities as possible in common with other children in general schools b) establishment of 400 special education center for children with severe disabilities at district

headquarters) provision for vocational education for the learning disabilities. The “Acharya Ramamurthy Committee suggested support for families having children with disability to improve educability. The revised Policy formulations and the NPE Program of Action 1992 recommended all schemes of education should be made responsible to children with physical and intellectual impairment. As we consider the scenario of state level Educational system has various stages such as pre-primary stage, primary stage in that lower primary, higher primary, secondary stage and higher secondary and higher stages. Once National objectives are framed, after that curriculum is framed then syllabus is framed and the books are printed for learning. Curriculum, syllabus and text books are the means of achieving the goals and objectives of education. In Every stage curriculum is designed differently according to the age group, maturity level and the needs of the learner. The primary objectives of curriculum are to make the students enable to speak, write, read and listen and to develop the oral and communication skill of the students.

In spite of same curriculum for one level of education and one syllabus for one particular std, all the goals and objectives are not fulfilled completely. Because there are individual difference in classrooms. The students have different abilities, different attitude, interest, maturity level and I. Q. level. There is heterogeneous group of students we can find in classes and schools. So we cannot compare the students on the basis of their I. Q., their interest, their attitude, their maturity level. In class we find some students who are below the average, and higher than average. But teacher has to teach one content with same teaching method to all but when he checks their understanding by asking questions orally or in written form, he realizes the differences among the students by observing their behavior or their responses. Some students give the response quickly and correctly but some students do not give response in limited time. If they give response it can be wrong and non relevant to the questions those students have some kind of lackness, it can be anything related to their learning sometimes sharp students may also have problems in their learning but the students with learning disabilities have severe problems that persist throughout their lives. Learning disabilities are defined as “a heterogeneous group of disorders manifested by significant difficulties in acquisition and use of listening, speaking, reading, writing, reasoning, or mathematical abilities” (National Joint Committee on Learning Disabilities [NJCLD], 1994, p. 65).

There are common types of Learning Disabilities such as

- Dyslexia-difficulty in reading, writing, spelling and speaking
- Dyscalculia-difficulty in math, understanding time, using money
- Dysgraphia –difficulty in writing, handwriting, spelling, organizing ideas
- Dyspraxia-difficulty in fine motor skills, eye co-ordination, balance, manual dexterity
- Dysphasia-difficulty in language
- Auditory Processing Disorder-difficulty in hearing differences between sounds
- Visual Processing Disorder –difficulty in interpreting visual information

For these students special education program helps them to compensate for these disorders. (Leasile Faught), 2005. So with the more instructional program we can give them better

learning opportunity, which will lead their future like normal children. The purpose of this study to find out learning disabilities of primary level students .

2. Need and Importance:

Learning disabilities are a wide variety of learning problems as we know there are individual difference in children likewise there are various learning disabilities among the students. We cannot identify the students by looking them. The L. D. children look like normal children. It is common misconception about learning disabilities that students cannot learn or they are less intelligent than their peers. Actually, learning disability is an ability to learn academic area is much lower than expected for his level of intelligence.

The identification of those students who has learning disability is very much crucial. Because after diagnosing their disabilities we can use different strategy for them for better learning. If the disabilities will remain as it is then it will be affect on them socially, physically and mentally. With the help of this research study researcher wants to find out the types of learning disabilities among the primary level children. Because it is a crucial stage of development of learning. While taking review of related research worldwide efforts are taken for the learning disabled but in India there is less no of research has done on the Learning disabilities, so Researcher wish to do research in this area. Researcher realizes if their disabilities will not diagnose and they won't get such solution for better learning they will not be able to do study or like normal student. So, researcher realizes the importance and seriousness of the disabilities problem and with the help of s

3. Title of Research

Study of Educational Institutes regarding Provisions and Facilities for Learning disable students.

4. Statement of Research

To do study of educational Institutes regarding provision and facilities for learning disable students at primary level in Urban Nashik.

5. Definitions

A-Conceptual Definitions

1. Educational Institutes-It is a place where people of various age gain an education which provides a large variety of learning environment and learning space.(www.wikipedia.org)

2. Provision and Facilities: The act of providing or supplying things.(www.freedictionary.com)

3. Learning Disability:

Learning disabilities are neurological difference in processing information that severely limits a person's ability to learn in specific skill area.

(Pahuja, P.N-Psychology of learning and development P-49)

Learning disability is a generic term that refers to heterogeneous group of disorder manifested by significant difficulties in the acquisition and use of listening, speaking, reading and writing and reasoning and mathematical abilities.

(National Joint committee for Learning disabilities 1981)

4. Urban Nashik Nashik is an ancient city in the northwest region of Maharashtra in India, Nashik is the third largest city of Maharashtra after Mumbai and Pune. (<https://nashik.gov.in>)

5. Primary Level: First stage of formal education, after preschool and before secondary education. (Wikipedia)

B. Operational Definitions

1. Educational Institutes-Institutions which provides knowledge and learning environment from Nashik Urban.

2. Provision and Facilities: Special Treatment or Special Department for LD.

3. Learning Disabilities: A disorder or difficulties in learning basic skills of Educational Institutes from Urban Nashik

4. Urban Nashik: Nashik is an ancient holy city third in Maharashtra

5. Primary Level: Std 1st to 5th of Educational Institutes from Nashik.

6. Objectives:

1) To identify the Educational Institutions of Urban Nashik working for learning disable students at Primary level.

2) To check the existing status of types of learning disable students and facilities provided in Educational Institutes of Urban Nashik at primary level.

7 Assumptions:

1. Students are lacking in developing the skills of LSRW at Primary level due to certain problems.

2. There are different types of disabilities in students at primary level.

8. Research Questions:

1) How many Educational Institutions of Urban Nashik are working for learning disable students at Primary level?

2) What is the existing status of types of learning disable students of Educational Institutes at the primary level?

9. Scope and Limitation of Research:

1. Scope

1) This research study is about learning disable students including boys and girls.

2) This research study covers the area and Educational Institutes of Urban Nasik.

2. Limitations:

1) The conclusions of research are depending on the data of respondent.

2) This research study has covered only Primary level students of Urban Nashik.

10. Method of present research:

In this present research Survey method is used.

Objective 1.

To identify the Educational Institutions of Urban Nashik working for learning disable students at Primary level.

For the present objective it was important to do the survey of Educational Institutes of Urban Nashik to identify how many institutions are working for learning disable students at primary level.

Objective 2.

To check the existing status of types of learning disable students of Educational Institutes Urban Nashik at primary level.

For the present objective survey was done with the help of questionnaire to know the exact status of different types learning disable students and facilities provided at primary level from Urban Nashik Educational Institutes.

11. Population and sampling:

All English Medium Schools from Urban Nashik were the population and 30 English medium schools and institutions were selected by Lottery method.

12. Data collection tool in present research:

For the first objective of research to find out the institutions who have identified learning disabilities, researcher has made one questionnaire.

Explanation of researcher made Test-

In researcher made test there are 15 questions which are objectives as well as descriptive. Test was in English and it was made for all the English medium schools of Nashik urban area to collect the information about total number of identified learning disable students in their school, types of learning disabilities identified the method of identifying learning disabilities, nature of remedial program etc. For this test Guidance from 11 experts were taken and done modification as per suggestions.

13. Data Analysis tools and Techniques:

In this present research for data analysis following statistical tool is used:

1. Percentage

Graph No1 Number of Institutions working for LD

Objective 2- To check the existing status of types of learning disabled students of English Medium Educational Institutions of Urban Nashik at primary level.

Table No-2 Number of learning disabilities students in Educational Institutions/Institutions

Sr. No	Details	Numbers	Percentage
1	Number of Educational Institutions have LD	11	37%
2	Number of Educational Institutions don't have LD	19	63%
	Total	30	100

Interpretation-As per the data received 37% Educational Institutions have learning disabled students in their Educational Institutions and 63% Educational Institutions do not have learning disabilities in their school.

Graph-2 Total no of Learning Disabled students in Educational Institutions/Institutions

Table -3 Total number of work experience of the special educator/Counselor for LD students

Sr.No	Response	Numbers	%
1	1 to 5 yrs	12	67
2	6 to 10 yrs	4	22
3	11 to 15 yrs	2	11
4	More than 15 yrs	0	0
	Total	18	100

Graph-3 Work experience of Special educator for LD students

Interpretation - As per the data received 67% Special educators are working for LD students between 1 to 5 years ,22% Special educators are working between 6 to 10 years,11% Special educators are working between 11 to 15, and no teacher is working more than 15 years .

Table-4 Methods of identifying the learning disable students at primary level in Educational Institutions / Institutions

Sr.No	Response	Numbers	%
1	By Observation Method	3	17
2	By Curriculum test method	13	72
3	By Testing IQ	0	0
4	Screening Test/Psychometric test	2	11
	Total	18	100

Graph-4 Methods used for Identifying LD

Interpretation-As per the data received 17% Special educators have used observation method,72% Special educators have used Curriculum test method, 11% special educators have used Screening test and IQ method was not used by any special educator for identifying the LD students.

Table 5-Total number of students are identified as a learning disable students at primary level in Educational Institutions /Institutions.

Sr.No	Range	Total Numbers of student	%
1	0-5	4	0.00025
2	6-10	14	9
3	11-15	-	0
4	16-20	20	13
5	21-25	22	14
6	26-30	-	0
7	More than 30-100	100	63
	Total	160	100

Graph -5 Total No of Identified LD students

Interpretation-As per the data received 0.00025% students have identified as a LD in 0-to 5 range, 9% LD students have identified in 0 to 10 range, no student identified in 11to 15 range,13% students have identified in 16 to 20 range,14% students have identified in 21 to 25 range, no student identified in 26 to 30 range and 63% students have identified in 30 to 100 range.

Table-6 -Categorization of LD students as per the types of disabilities in Educational Institutions

Sr. No	Response	Numbers	%
1	Yes	11	37
2	No	19	63
	Total	30	100

Graph-6 Categorization of LD students as per types of disabilities

Interpretation-As per the data received 37% Educational Institutions have categorized learning disable students in their Educational Institutions and 63% Educational Institutions do not have categorized learning disabilities in their school.

Table-7 The types of learning disable students identified at primary level in Educational Institutions.

Sr. No	Response	Numbers	%
1	Dyslexia	157	98
2	Dyscalculia	0	0
3	Dysgraphia	0	0
4	Dyspraxia	0	0
5	Dysphasia	0	0
6	Auditory Processing Disorder	0	0
7	Visual Processing Disorder	3	2
	Total	160	100

Graph-7 Types of Disabilities Identified

Interpretation-As per the data received 98% students have identified Dyslexia and 2% students have identified visual processing disorder.

Table -8 Provision of Remedial/Special programs for learning disable student’s Educational Institutions to improve their learning.

Sr. No	Response	Numbers	%
1	Yes	18	60
2	No	12	40
	Total	30	100

Graph -8 Status of Provision of Remedial program in Educational Institutions

Interpretation-As per the data received 60% Educational Institutions have Provision of Remedial program for learning disable students in their Educational Institutions and 40% Educational Institutions do not have Provision of Remedial program learning disabilities in their school.

Table -9Provision of remedial /special program as per the type of disability of students to improve their learning.

Sr. No	Response	Numbers	%
1	Yes	11	37
2	No	19	63
	Total	30	100

Graph -9 Provision of Remedial program as per type of disability

Interpretation-As per the data received 37 % Educational Institutions have Provision of Remedial program for learning disable students as per the types of disability in their Educational Institutions and 63 % Educational Institutions do not have Provision of Remedial program learning disabilities as per the types of disability in their school

Table -10Total number of Educational Institutions have Special/Trained teachers to teach to the learning disable students.

Sr. No	Response	Numbers	%
1	Yes	18	60
2	No	12	40
	Total	30	100

Graph -10 Availability of Special Educator/Counsellor for LD students

Interpretation-As per the data received 60 % Educational Institutions have Special Educator/Counsellor for learning disable students in their Educational Institutions and 40% Educational Institutions do not have Special Educator/Counsellor for learning disabilities in their school.

Table -11 Total number of Educational Institutions have Counseling cell /Department in school/institution

Sr.No	Response	Numbers	%
1	Yes	18	60
2	No	12	40
	Total	30	100

Graph -11 Total Number of Educational Institutions /Institutions have Counseling cell

Interpretation-As per the data received 60 % Educational Institutions have counselling cells in their Educational Institutions and 40 % Educational Institutions do not have Counselling cells in their school.

Table -12. Total number of Educational Institutions have Educational Counselor to deal with the learning disable students.

Sr. No	Response	Numbers	%
1	Yes	11	37
2	No	19	63
	Total	30	100

Graph -12 Availability of Educational Counselor in School/Institutions

Interpretation-As per the data received 37% Educational Institutions have Educational Counsellor in their Educational Institutions and 63% Educational Institutions do not have Educational Counsellor in their school.

13. Categorization method of learning disabled students

- a. On the basis of type of disability
- b. On the basis of learning material facility available

14. Nature of remedy/special program as per the type of disability of students to improve their skills.

- a. Individual Educational Planning.
- b. Learning by doing activities.
- c. Parents involvement in remedial activities.
- d. Mind engaging activities.
- e. Job sheets exercises

15. Details of special training of Special Educator/Counsellor

- a. RCI Registered B. Ed
- b. PG Diploma Course
- c. Remedial Teaching Training
- d. Certificate Course in Remedial Teaching
- e. M.A. Clinical Psychology
- f. Short term online courses for LD

16. Expertise area of Special Educator/ Counsellor

- a. Individual Educational Planning for LD and slow learners
- b. One to one counselling
- c. Counselling on behavioral problems
- d. Conductions of Awareness sessions for educators and parents.

14. Findings:

In this present research study, the conclusions are presented as per the objectives.

Objective 1.

To identify the Educational Institutions of Urban Nashik working for learning disable students at Primary level.

For the present objective survey of Educational Institutes of Urban Nashik was done to identify how many institutions are working for learning disable students at primary level through questionnaire.

Following is the conclusion drawn after data analysis.

1. 50% English medium schools are working for learning disable students and 10 % NGO's are working for learning disabilities remaining 40% schools are not working for learning disable students.

Objective 2.

To check the existing status of types of learning disable students of Educational Institutes of Urban Nashik at primary level.

For the present objective survey was done with the help of questionnaire to know the exact status of different types of learning disable students and facilities provision to them at primary level from Urban Nashik Educational Institutes.

1. 37% schools have learning disable students in their schools and 63% schools do not have learning disabilities in their school.(Table No-1)
2. 67% Special educators are working for LD students between 1 to 5 years ,22% Special educators are working between 6 to 10 years,11% Special educators are working between 11 to 15, and no teacher is working more than 15 years.(Table No-2)
3. 17% Special educators have used observation method, 72% Special educators have used Curriculum test method, 11% special educators have used Screening test and IQ method was not used by any special educator for identifying the LD students.(Table No-3)
4. 0.00025% students have identified as a LD in 0-to 5 range, 9% LD students have identified in 0 to 10 range, no student identified in 11to 15 range,13% students have identified in 16 to 20 range,14% students have identified in 21 to 25 range, no student identified in 26 to 30 range and 63% students have identified in 30 to 100 range.(Table No-4)
5. 37% schools have categorized learning disable students in their schools and 63% schools do not have categorized learning disabilities in their school.(Table No-5)
6. 98% students have identified Dyslexia and 2% students have identified visual processing disorder.(Table No-6)
7. 60% schools have Provision of Remedial program for learning disable students in their schools and 40% schools do not have Provision of Remedial program for learning disabilities in their school.(Table No-7)
8. 37 % schools have Provision of Remedial program for learning disable students as per the types of disability in their schools and 63 % schools do not have Provision of Remedial program learning disabilities as per the types of disability in their school.(Table No-8)

9. 60 % schools have Special Educator/Counsellor for learning disable students in their schools and 40% schools do not have Special Educator/Counsellor for learning disabilities in their school.(Table No-9)

10.60 % schools have counselling cells in their Schools and 40 % schools do not have Counselling cells in their school.(Table No-10)

11.37% schools have Educational Counsellor in their schools and 63% schools do not have Educational Counsellor in their school.(Table No-11)

12. Categorization method used for learning disabled students in different schools are as follows:

- a. On the basis of type of disability
- b. On the basis of learning material facility available

13 In different schools' remedy/special program implemented as per the type of disability of students to improve their skills as follows:

- a. Individual Educational Planning.
- b. Learning by doing activities.
- c. Parents involvement in remedial activities.
- d. Mind engaging activities.
- e. Job sheets exercises

14 Details of Qualifications or special training of Special Educator/Counsellor in different schools are as follows:

- a. RCI Registered B. Ed
- b. PG Diploma Course
- c. Remedial Teaching Training
- d. Certificate Course in Remedial Teaching
- e. M.A. Clinical Psychology
- f. Short term online courses for LD

15. Expertise area of Special Educator/ Counsellor in different schools:

- a. Individual Educational Planning for LD and slow learners
- b. One to one counselling
- c. Counselling on behavioral problems
- d. Conductions of Awareness sessions for educators and parents.

15.Recommendations:

1. In schools special attention needs to give to learning disable students to enhance their basic skills.
2. Every School should have Special educator and Counsellor to help learning disable students to attain mastery level in their basic skills.
3. Not only special educators but regular teachers also need to use various strategies, games, exercise, tools in their teaching learning process.
4. Identifiation of Learning disabilities needs to done in every school to plan set of strategies to help LD students.
5. Dignosis of weak areas in basic skills need to be done by teachers and special educators.

6. Parents should also include in Identification of Learning disabilities and Diagnosis of weak areas in basic skills so that they can also provide support to teachers to enhance the basic skills of their children.

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